

The association of motor competence and executive function across primary school years

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ABSTRACT

Motor competence and executive function (i.e., top-down control of behavior) have been suggested to co-develop due to shared neural substrates. However, components of executive function show different developmental trajectories, so that it remains unclear how age affects interrelations between both domains. We therefore investigated the strength and stability of the association between motor competence and components of executive function across cohorts representing different grades. 400 Swiss girls and boys attending grades 1 (7 y) to 5 (11 y) completed age-appropriate versions of the MOBAC test battery to assess motor competence. Additionally, we administered a modified Flanker task including both standard and switching blocks as well as an N-back task to examine inhibitory control, task-switching and working memory. Path-analysis including all participants revealed a low to moderate association between motor competence and all components of executive function. However, the strength and stability of the association differed across grade levels. Higher motor competence was consistently related to better inhibitory control in all subgroups, but its association with task-switching and working memory was limited to specific grade levels. In conclusion, the association between motor competence and inhibitory control is characterized by stability across the first five school grades, whereas the association with its separable components follows a non-linear trend. This provides an indication that motor competence interventions have the potential to influence executive function components differently depending on the developmental period.

1. Introduction

Executive function refers to a set of general-purpose control processes that regulate one's thoughts and behaviors (Miyake & Friedman, 2012). The conceptualization of this construct is still a matter of debate, but a review of different executive function models has indicated that inhibitory control (i.e., resist distractions and suppress prepotent responses), working memory updating (i.e., encode, update and retrieve information) and task-switching (i.e. shift between mental sets) have consistently been identified as underlying abilities (Baggetta & Alexander, 2016). These abilities act in concert to allow self-regulated learning and contribute to academic performance, so that both intra- and interindividual differences in executive function have a predictive value for the development of math and reading skills (Willoughby et al., 2019). Executive function further shapes the students' behavior in and outside the classroom as it is prospectively and inversely associated with externalizing and internalizing behavioral problems (Yang et al., 2022).

Given that executive function is characterized by recurring patterns of high sensitivity to the environment (Thompson & Steinbeis, 2020), there is a large interest in modifiable factors that allow the promotion of its development.

Motor competence has the potential to influence this cognitive domain based on a prominent developmental framework (Piaget & Inhelder, 1966): Motor and cognitive development appear to be inter-related as building motor competences in early life open up further opportunities to explore and interact with the environment. Unfolding these competences are therefore seen as conditional factor for the development of more complex and differentiated cognitive abilities. For example, a toddler that learns to stack blocks needs to adjust the own strategy, if a block does not fit. Such an accommodation is essential for the refinement of problem solving (an ability that combines different aspects of executive function) schemas, but this opportunity depends on the ability of the toddler to move and manipulate objects. The interrelation of motor and cognitive domains is also key to recent models of

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embodied cognition, which assume that executive function is grounded in the ability to control and plan motor actions (Gentsch et al., 2016). This idea is supported by longitudinal findings underlining the predictive value of motor competences in infancy for executive function at later stages (Gottwald et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2017). From a neuroscience perspective, interrelations between both domains have been attributed to an activation of joint cerebral networks during motor tasks and those with high executive function demands (Leisman et al., 2016). The dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, the anterior cingulate cortex and parietal cortices form a higher-order executive control network that is activated similarly across tasks probing inhibitory control, working memory and task-switching, whereas the recruitment of the basal ganglia and cerebellum appears to be task-specific (Niendam et al., 2012). The cerebellum and the prefrontal cortex also underlie the performance of motor tasks, with only the latter showing a gradual decrease in activation over the skill acquisition process due to an increase in automaticity (Lohse et al., 2014). Evidence in support of joint neural substrates is also provided by the observation of similar activation patterns between motor execution and motor imagery (Hardwick et al., 2018), even though motor imagery is thought to rely more on executive resources (Glover et al., 2020). The link between motor and cognitive skills has been explained by the motor system allowing cognition to evolve for developing off-line control until behavioral automaticity is achieved (Koziol et al., 2012).

In children, research on the relation between both constructs has focused on the predictive value of motor competence due to its potential to influence multiple health-related aspects during development (Barnett et al., 2022; Hill et al., 2024), including body fat (Lima et al., 2017) and physical fitness (Luz et al., 2017). Motor competence reflects the individual's ability to perform a variety of motor acts that are necessary to engage in physical activity and to manage everyday tasks and encompass movement coordination and control underlying a specific motor outcome (Barnett et al., 2016). In this respect, locomotion (i.e., spatial movement of the own body), object control (i.e., the manipulation of objects in space) and stability (i.e., maintain postural control) are commonly understood as subdomains of motor competence (Robinson et al., 2015). The current evidence suggests a moderating role of motor competence for exercise-induced benefits for executive function (Hill et al., 2024) as well as a direct positive relation between both domains in children and adolescents aged 9–18 years, with no influence of age (Bao et al., 2024). In contrast, a quantitative synthesis that focused on a narrow age range found an increase of the magnitude of the correlation between aspects of motor competence and inhibitory control in particular with age (Gandotra et al., 2022). A direct comparison of younger and older children also supported differences in the strength of the relation between motor competence and executive function, but in the opposite direction (Albuquerque et al., 2022).

These inconsistencies may be due to the investigation of age as moderator in studies with a narrow age range and the assumption of a linear relation or development of both constructs. A similar criticism has been expressed with regard to conclusions on periods that appear to be sensitive to physical activity (Northey et al., 2024), which serves as a correlate of motor competence. Thus, linearity and non-linearity in changes in motor and cognitive domains both need to be considered. Longitudinal findings highlight that even across a short period of two years, children are characterized by both a high variability in individual trajectories of motor competence development and a less pronounced change, when their age at baseline is higher (Coppens et al., 2019). The variability in motor competence further seems to increase from 5 to 10 years, given that delays in development are more frequently observed in older children (Ré et al., 2018). These trajectories in motor competence do not necessarily coincide with developmental changes in executive function across all age groups. A pooled analyses of large cohorts showed that executive function undergoes significant age-related changes until adolescence, which are to great extent driven by domain-general abilities (Teruo-Clemmens et al., 2023). However, a

synthesis of studies investigating the factor structure of executive function has revealed a differentiation of underlying abilities indicated by a transition from an unidimensional to an unitary/diversity model with ongoing maturation (Karr et al., 2018). In addition to changes in the interrelation of working memory, task-switching and inhibitory control (Zelazo & Carlson, 2012), the modification of factor structure may also result from differing developmental growth patterns. Task-switching achieves a mature state in adolescence, whereas working memory updating has a more protracted development that continues until young-adulthood (Huizinga et al., 2006). With regard to the common component of executive function, variability is evident from a much earlier maturation of the ability to suppress a motor response relative to the inhibition on a cognitive level (Fernández et al., 2021; Richardson et al., 2018). Given these specific trajectories, conclusions on the stability of the association between motor competence and executive function across different developmental periods require multiple assessments that allow for the examination of different types of trends (i.e., linear vs. non-linear). An alternative to repeated measures within participants are the comparison of interrelations between constructs across cohorts differing in age.

Using this approach, we investigated the association of children's motor competence and executive function within grades 1 to 5. Possible differences in strength of relations were considered by the investigation of correlations with inhibitory control, task-switching and working memory. Based on previous meta-analytical findings, we expected a small positive association between motor competence and each component of executive function in the pooled analyses (Bao et al., 2024; Gandotra et al., 2022), whereas we derived no hypothesis on the trend across 5 grades due to a lack of findings on changes in the strength of the association across these age groups.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

The data for this cross-sectional analysis has been collected from a subsample ($N = 400$) of the study "Development of basic motor competencies in children (EMOKK)" (2021–2025). This subsample was recruited from grade 1 (7 y) to 5 (11 y) classes at a local school in Basel, Switzerland and participants completed cognitive tests in addition to a motor competence test battery. Children attending these classes were invited for study participation and no exclusion criteria were set. Legal guardians of the participants received information on the purpose of the study and provided informed written consent. The study protocol was submitted to and approved by the Ethics Commission of the University of Zurich, Switzerland (No. 21.2.5) and procedures were in line with the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki (and its amendments).

2.2. Study design

Data collection was performed within the first two weeks in February 2023. Participants completed the MOBAC test battery as well as computerized Flanker task and N-Back in the school setting. Cognitive testing was performed prior to the assessment of motor competences and both types of instruments were administered on the same day. The time of assessments was equally distributed across grades to minimize the risk of an impact of the diurnal variation on the outcomes. Additionally, we collected anthropometric data (weight, height, body mass index) and asked legal guardians of participants to report their child's biological sex and birth. They further completed an item on language comprehension ("How well does your child speak the language that is spoken by the teachers in school?"), which had to be rated on Likert scale (1 = bad, 2 = rather bad, 3 = rather good, 4 = good).

2.3. Motor competence

Key concepts for consideration of motor competence assessment across grades include the feasibility for group administration, the cultural significance of underlying skills and the ability developmental and interindividual differences (Hulteen et al., 2023). These needs were addressed by using the MOBAK test battery, which measures basic and grade-specific motor competencies that are targeted by Swiss physical education curricula (Herrmann, 2018; Herrmann & Seelig, 2020) and allows the discrimination of competency profiles (Herrmann & Seelig, 2017). The instrument was administered class-wise in the school setting. Classes were split into groups of 3–4 participants and a trained test leader examined each group. Motor competence was evaluated from eight items, which were demonstrated prior to assessment: balancing, rolling, jumping, running, throwing, catching, bouncing and dribbling. The risk of ceiling effects on scores were minimized by administering age-appropriate versions of the items (i.e., MOBAK 1–2 to grade 1 and 2, MOBAK 3–4 to grade 3 and 4, MOBAK 5–6 to grade 5). For throwing and catching, participants had six consecutive attempts per task. The scoring was 0 for up to 2 successful attempts, 1 for 3 to 4 successful attempts and 2 for 5 to 6 successful attempts. For the other test items, participants had two runs each (without practice trials), which were scored 0 for a fail and 1 for a pass per attempt. The scores were summed up, so that up to 16 points could be scored for an overall motor competence rating.

2.4. Cognitive testing

The Flanker and N-Back tasks are considered prototypical executive function tasks that assess inhibitory control and working memory updating (Diamond, 2013), respectively. Along with a modified version of the Flanker that allows the measurement of task-switching (Lee et al., 2013), these variants have been frequently applied to capture developmental and inter-individual differences (Karr et al. 2018, 2022). Computerized and age-appropriate versions of the Flanker and N-Back tasks were administered with E-Prime 3.0 (PST, PA, USA). This approach reduces the risk of ceiling effects, given that presentation times and response windows can be scaled, and increases sensitivity by logging responses at millisecond precision over a high number of trials. Cognitive tests were performed class-wise in a group setting to be comparable to the assessment situation of the MOBAK battery. Computerized assessment of executive function have been cross-validated with individual assessments and showed comparable test-retest reliability, associations with known covariates and even had a greater predictive power for school-related outcomes (Obradović et al., 2018). Each participant was seated in front of a laptop, with a viewing distance of approximately 80 cm. Two experimenters introduced the cognitive tasks and provided instructions with the aid of visual material. The Flanker and N-Back tasks were preceded by examples showing the trial procedure with visual stimuli and available responses. Additionally, a set of 25 practice trials were administered to familiarize participants with the cognitive testing. For the assessment of behavioral performance, the lighting in the room was dimmed and noise reduced to a minimum.

The Flanker task included standard and switching blocks that were modified to assess task-switching (Ludyga et al., 2019). During the standard blocks, five white fish were presented against black background. Participants were instructed to feed the fish in the center by pressing a button corresponding facing in the direction of the mouth of the fish. The central fish was flanked by four fish facing in the same (congruent trials) or a different direction (incongruent trials). Both trial types were presented with equal probability and their order was randomized. Following two standard blocks with 32 trials each, a new task was introduced. Blue fish were presented against black background and participants were asked to respond to the direction of the flanking fish and ignore the fish in the center. After a familiarization with the task, two switching blocks with 32 trials each were administered. During these blocks, white and blue fish were both used as stimuli, so that

participants had to switch rules based on their color (i.e., attend either the flanking or central fish). No switch and switch trials occurred with equal probability and followed a pseudo-randomized order (e.g., AAB-BAB). Congruent and incongruent trials were nested with an equal distribution across the switch and no switch conditions. On both standard and switching blocks of the Flanker task, the presentation latencies were identical. Following an inter-trial interval that varied randomly between 600 and 900 ms, visual stimuli were presented until a response was given or the response window was exceeded (2500 in grades 1 to 2, 2000 ms in grade 3 and 1500 ms in grades 4 to 5). Feedback on the direction of the response was provided over 250 ms by displaying fish food to the left or right of the fish. Mean reaction times on response-correct trials and accuracy rates were calculated separately for congruent and incongruent trials on standard blocks and switch and no switch trials on switching blocks. Trials with responses faster than 120 ms were removed from the analysis to reduce the impact of guesses. Accuracy rates on incongruent trials and switch trials served as main outcomes for inhibitory control and task-switching, respectively.

During the modified N-Back task, a single white or blue fish displayed in a 3 x 2 grid matrix served as visual stimulus. The fish changed its spatial location across 6 squares. Participants were instructed to keep track of its position and indicate whether the fish occurred at the same position in the previous trial by pressing one of two buttons that corresponded to yes or no. Depending on the participants' school grade, difficulty was adjusted by showing a single white fish (grades 1 to 3) or by alternating white and blue fish (grades 4 to 5). The latter required updating the spatial locations separately for the differently colored fish. In all variants of the task, targets appeared with a probability of 0.33 and their location was equally distributed across the grid matrix. Each trial started with the display of an empty grid matrix over a latency range that varied randomly between 600 and 900 ms. Subsequently, a single fish was presented at one of six locations until a response was collected. Feedback on the response was provided for 250 ms. The N-Back task included two blocks with 27 trials each. For both targets and non-targets, mean reaction times on response-correct trials and accuracy rates were calculated. Similar to the Flanker task, trials with responses faster than 120 ms were dedicated as guesses and were removed from the analysis. The adjusted hit rate served as main outcome for working memory and was derived as the difference between accuracy rate on targets and error rate on non-targets.

2.5. Statistical analysis

SPSS 29.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA) and the AMOS graphical interface were used for statistical analyses. The Chi-Square Goodness of Fit test was used to compare distribution of sex and language skills across grades. Preliminary analysis investigated the test-retest reliability of the primary outcomes of the cognitive tasks across a period of one year. The intra-class correlation coefficients varied between 0.65 and 0.84 (Table S1). For main analysis, we used path-analyses to predict task-switching, inhibitory control and working memory by motor competence, while covariances were estimated between the error terms of the three endogenous variables. The outcomes of the cognitive assessments were z-transformed for each grade level prior to path-analyses to increase comparability despite the use of age-appropriate test versions. Separate fully saturated models were specified to examine the association of motor competence and executive function in the full cohort, girls only, boys only as well as both sexes at grades 1 to 5. In the pooled analyses, relations were displayed separately for boys and girls due to evidence indicating that sex influences the effect of motor skill training on executive function (Ludyga et al., 2020). The main models using accuracy-based measures was followed-up by a secondary analyses using speed of processing metrics, which served to check for a speed-accuracy trade-off. When an association of higher motor skills with increased speed of processing accompanied the association of higher motor skills with higher accuracy rates on executive function task

or vice versa, such a trade-off was identified. All models were controlled for body mass index and sex (except for the models using girls or boys only) as they are suggested to influence executive function (Mamrot & Hanć, 2019; Wierenga et al., 2019). The full information maximum likelihood was applied to calculate parameter estimates despite missing data. Standardized regression coefficients were calculated to assess the magnitude of the strength of associations, with categories being low ($\beta = 0.1$ to 0.29), moderate ($\beta = 0.3$ to 0.49) and high ($\beta \geq 0.50$). Additionally, *t*-Tests were used to test whether regression coefficients equal zero and this hypothesis was rejected at $p < 0.05$. For each grade level and executive function component, the corresponding *p*-values were displayed in heat maps. A post-hoc power analysis was conducted on paths predicting different executive function components (accuracy-based measures) from motor competence within and across grade levels to check whether the sample size was sufficient to detect associations at 80 % power.

3. Results

Cognitive tests were completed by 400 participants, of which 335 also engaged in the MOBAK assessments. The proportion of girls (44.9 % in grade 1, 46.8 % in grade 2, 51.7 % in grade 3, 48.8 % in grade 4, and 48.1 % in grade 5) did not differ across the cohorts, $X^2(4, 400) = 0.80$, $p = 0.938$. Similarly, the number of participants that can speak and understand the language spoken by the teacher well (87.8 % in grade 1, 95.7 % in grade 2, 93.9 % in grade 3, 93.8 % in grade 4, and 90.5 % in grade 5) was distributed equally across the grades, $X^2(4, 374) = 10.77$, $p = 0.549$. The participants' characteristics, their MOBAK score and cognitive performance are displayed in Table 1. The MOBAK scores and cognitive performance for boys and girls are shown in Table S2 and Table S3 (Supplement), respectively. The percentage of complete data per variable varied between 84.9 and 100.0 for the full cohort (Table S4, Supplement).

3.1. All grades

In the pooled analysis that combined all grades (Fig. 1), there was a low-to-moderate association of higher motor competence with a higher accuracy on switching trials, $\beta = 0.29$, $p < 0.001$, a higher accuracy on incongruent trials, $\beta = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$, and a higher adjusted hit-rate, $\beta = 0.17$, $p = 0.006$. When the model used speed of processing measures, motor competence was inversely associated with reaction time on incongruent trials, $\beta = -0.25$, $p < 0.001$, but there was no relation with task-switching and working memory outcomes.

When the models were estimated for boys and girls only, the association between motor competence and task-switching, $\beta = 0.26$ (f)/ $\beta = 0.22$ (m), $p < 0.001$ (f)/ $p = 0.003$ (m), as well as inhibitory control, $\beta = 0.26$ (f)/ $\beta = 0.32$ (m), $p < 0.001$ (f)/ $p < 0.001$ (m), were maintained at small-to-moderate levels for both sexes (Fig. S1, Supplement). In

contrast, the relation of motor competence and working memory was low and only reached statistical significance in boys, $\beta = 0.14$ (f)/ $\beta = 0.18$ (m), $p = 0.074$ (f)/ $p = 0.019$ (m). In models that used speed of processing outcomes (Fig. S2, Supplement), higher motor competence was weakly associated with lower reaction time on incongruent trials only in both girls and boys, $\beta = -0.26$ (f)/ $\beta = -0.23$ (m), $p = 0.001$ (f)/ $p = 0.002$ (m).

3.2. Subgroups

Higher motor competence was associated with a higher accuracy on incongruent trials of the Flanker task across all grades (Fig. 2), $\beta = 0.23$ to 0.41 , $p = 0.001$ to 0.040 . With the exception of grade 4, a higher accuracy on switching trials was predicted by higher motor competence, $\beta = 0.26$ to 0.49 , $p = 0.001$ to 0.033 . In contrast, a positive relation between the adjusted hit-rate on N-Back and motor competence was observed in grade 2 only, $\beta = 0.38$, $p = 0.001$. The post-hoc power analysis supported that 80 % power was achieved for all regression paths (Table S5), except for the negligible association of motor competence and working memory in grade 3.

When the model included speed of processing-based measures instead of accuracy, the standardized regression coefficients for the association between motor competence, task-switching and working memory were not significantly different from zero (Fig. 3), $\beta = -0.13$ to 0.18 , $p = 0.124$ to 0.884 . However, a higher motor competence was related to faster reaction time on incongruent trials of the Flanker task across grades 1,3 and 5, $\beta = -0.29$ to -0.39 , $p = 0.001$ to 0.017 . Consequently, there is no indication for a speed-accuracy trade-off across the different components of executive function and grades.

4. Discussion

The pooled analysis of all participants supported higher motor competence to be related to better executive function in both boys and girls. The strength of this association was low-to-moderate for inhibitory control as well as task-switching and low for working memory. Our findings advance the understanding of the predictive value of motor competence for executive function by showing that these associations varied in strength and stability across grades 1 to 5.

The link we found between both constructs has been hypothesized by different theoretical frameworks. From a developmental perspective, motor experiences have been determined as essential stimuli for the unfolding of cognitive abilities and executive function in particular (Foglia & Wilson, 2013; Piaget & Inhelder, 1966). In this respect, evidence from infants suggests that by interacting with the environment, they extract and build up a system of knowledge for guiding actions (Hofsten 2009). Thus, if motor competences are refined to enable more complex motor acts (Barnett et al., 2016), they are likely to be embedded in more complex task demands that exercise a set of cognitive processes

Table 1
Participants' characteristics, MOBAK score, and cognitive performance displayed for grades 1 to 5.

	Grade 1 (N = 30 f/38 m)		Grade 2 (N = 36 f/41 m)		Grade 3 (N = 45 f/41 m)		Grade 4 (N = 42 f/44 m)		Grade 5 (N = 38 f/41 m)	
	M	SD								
Age in y	7.1	0.3	8.2	0.4	9.2	0.4	10.1	0.4	11.3	0.4
Weight in kg	23.8	3.5	27.6	5.2	31.3	6.3	36.2	6.8	39.9	7.7
BMI in kg·m ⁻²	15.5	1.5	15.9	2.2	16.6	2.5	17.4	2.6	18.0	2.8
MOBAK	9.6	2.9	12.6	2.3	8.0	3.0	9.7	2.9	8.3	3.6
Incon. AR	0.90	0.10	0.93	0.11	0.95	0.10	0.93	0.11	0.94	0.10
Switch AR	0.72	0.16	0.77	0.15	0.76	0.14	0.72	0.14	0.77	0.13
Adj. Hit-rate	0.49	0.35	0.54	0.31	0.48	0.36	0.07	0.25	0.14	0.30
Incon. RT in ms	1036.1	266.0	878.6	247.3	684.2	181.1	565.3	128.9	516.4	115.3
Switch RT in ms	1348.3	348.2	1250.9	280.8	1036.3	195.5	857.5	169.1	834.5	159.3
Target RT in ms	1286.7	746.6	1114.0	534.8	833.1	417.6	968.3	559.1	869.9	350.1

Notes: Age appropriate versions of the MOBAK instrument (change of instrument from grade 2 to 3 and 4 to 5) and cognitive tests were administered. Adj. = adjusted; AR = accuracy rate; BMI = Body mass index; Incon. = Incongruent; RT = reaction time.

Fig. 1. Path model showing the prediction of task-switching, inhibitory control and working memory by motor competence. *Notes:* Standardized regression coefficients for accuracy- and speed of processing-based measures are shown above and below the lines, respectively. The models were controlled for sex and body mass index. * $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 2. Standardized regression coefficients for the association of motor competence and aspects of executive function derived from accuracy-based measures across grades (left panel) and p-values for their comparison against zero (right panel). *Notes:* Lines in the left panel were smoothed using spline interpolation. Measures include accuracy on switch trials (task-switching) and incongruent trials (inhibitory control) of the Flanker as well as adjusted hit-rate (working memory) derived from the N-back task. The color of the heat map represents the p-value of the regression, with a tendency towards sand indicating a lower error probability. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Standardized regression coefficients for the association of motor competence and aspects of executive function derived from speed of processing-based measures across grades (left panel) and p-values for their comparison against zero (right panel). *Notes:* Lines in the left panel were smoothed using spline interpolation. Measures include reaction time on switch trials (task-switching) and incongruent trials (inhibitory control) of the Flanker task as well as adjusted hit-rate (working memory) derived from the N-back task. The color of the heat map represents the p-value of the regression, with a tendency towards sand indicating a lower error probability. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

underlying executive function. This is also supported by longitudinal findings linking higher motor competences in children with a higher participation rate in organized sports, which in turn require the use of such competences in a more adaptive and flexible way (Drenowatz and Greier 2019; Fransen et al., 2014). For the motor test battery, this can be illustrated with the example of the throwing item. Participants scoring high on this task are qualified to engage in sports that require the adaptation of the competence to throw a ball with precision to a changing situation, such as in a handball game. While the administration of the test item requires inhibitory control mainly to focus on the current task in a controlled environment, the handball game will induce a greater load due to the necessity to resist a variety of distractions arising from changing locations of teammates, actions of the opponents, the

referee and the crowd (Wagner et al., 2014). Meta-analytical findings showing that young athletes show improved inhibitory control compared to non-athletes further support the interpretation that motor competences enable the engagement in more complex sports situations that exercise executive functions (Albaladejo-García et al., 2023).

This idea overlaps with the concept of reciprocity, which suggests that executive function and motor competences are separable constructs that influence each other and develop together (McClelland & Cameron, 2019). Integrating findings from neuroscience, this reciprocity can be explained by the idea of shared neural substrates (Kozioł et al., 2012; Lohse et al., 2014), which assumes that refinement of motor competences will also result in improvements in the other domain and vice versa. On a mechanistic level, this is evident from meta-analytical

findings showing similar changes in the activation of brain regions subserving executive function following targeted cognitive and motor skills training (Patel et al., 2013). Applied to the tasks used in this study, it appears that joint processes seem to contribute to performance on the MOBAK test battery and the Flanker as well as N-Back tasks (Ludyga et al., 2019). For example, tasks from both domains require the maintenance of the goal in working memory, the updating of plans related to achieving this goal, the focus of attention to task-relevant cues, sequencing of actions and additional cognitive control processes, even though they are embedded in different contexts. As executive function develop as domain-general abilities, their employment in specific contexts will likely yield transfer effects (Zelazo & Carlson, 2023).

Evidence in support of theoretical frameworks linking motor competences and executive function has been provided by a meta-analysis reporting small positive interrelations based on task performance (Bao et al., 2024). However, in this quantitative synthesis, individual components of executive function explained no significant proportion of variance of within- and between-study heterogeneity. Our findings support the same direction of effects, but a higher strength of the association for motor competence and the inhibitory as well as task-switching components of executive function. This pattern was observed for accuracy-based measures on the Flanker and N-Back tasks, with no indications of a speed-accuracy trade-off. Consequently, participants with higher motor competence showed a higher performance on executive function tasks rather than a simple strategy change from prevention (i.e., avoid mistakes) to promotion focus (i.e., respond quickly). Further examination of interrelations across grade levels revealed different trends for each component. While there was a low-to-moderate relation between motor competence and inhibitory control across all cohorts, working memory updating and task-switching showed a distinct pattern. The stability of cross-domain relations for inhibitory control, which was evident from both accuracy- and speed of processing-based measures, may be attributed to the structure of executive function. In first grades, the unidimensional construct, in which different components contribute similarly to a domain-general ability, seems to provide the best model fit (Karr et al., 2018). During the transition from childhood to adolescence, abilities underlying executive function develop differently and become separable (Laureys et al., 2022). A prominent conceptualization in this context is the consideration of inhibitory control as a domain-general component and both working memory updating and task-switching as nested subdomains (Miyake & Friedman, 2012). Consequently, inhibitory control can be viewed as a proxy of executive function across different grades, which allows the detection of a more general association between motor competence and this cognitive domain. Evidence in support of this view is provided by findings showing that different subdomains of motor competences are similarly related to inhibitory control (Chang & Gu, 2018; Gashaj et al., 2019).

In contrast, the specific relations between motor competence and other components of executive function were characterized by more variation between cohorts. Participants with higher motor competence showed a higher accuracy on switching trials of the Flanker task in all grades, except grade 4. This coincides with a reduction in accuracy rate compared to grade 3, although all other grades show an increasing trend. The latter reflects the maturation of the ability to shift between mental sets, which peaks around preadolescence (Huiszina and van der Molen 2007). The deviation from the trend at grade 4 may hint a reconfiguration of underlying abilities. Neuroimaging findings have shown that inter-individual differences in task-switching at this developmental stage depend on whether children are able to recruit frontoparietal networks in an adult-like manner or if they have to employ compensatory measures (Schwarze et al., 2023). Such specific mechanisms can account for a lack to detect interrelations between motor competences and task-switching as a reconfiguration does not necessarily coincide with major developments in the other domain at the same point in time. A distinct pattern for interrelations was also found for

working memory updating as motor competence explained a statistically significant proportion of variance in the adjusted hit rate in grade 2 only. Similar to task-switching, differences in accuracy measures were not affected by a compensation in speed of processing-based outcomes as reaction times on the N-Back task were not related to motor competence in any grade level. The variation in the strength of associations may be due to differing developmental trajectories. Motor competence is subject to a linear positive change in the first school years (Coppens et al., 2019). Working memory also shows a rapid growth in this period, but follows a non-linear trend with a brief accelerated phase of development during adolescence (Ahmed et al., 2022). The association between both constructs could therefore be limited to or be more pronounced for developmental periods characterized by a shared, accelerated growth and/or a similar linear change.

Although our findings provide indications on the stability and magnitude of the association between motor competence and executive function in grades 1 to 5, it should be noted that we compared these associations between and not within cohorts across time. This allows less control on confounding factors, so that potential differences in socioeconomic status and parents' education between subgroups could have affected comparability of results across grade levels. However, we recruited all classes from a single public school to reduce any risks arising from different locations. Additionally, we used only a single test battery to assess motor competence and one cognitive task per executive function component. This prevented the comparison of the associations between both domains based on different executive function models that differ in factor structure. The type of tests applied can further affect the strength of associations between constructs and lead to a false negative (type 2 error), if any of them are subject to ceiling effects (Hill et al., 2024). Age-appropriate versions of the MOBAK test, the Flanker and N-Back tasks were used to address this on the study design level. While this approach prevented ceiling effects, the use of these versions (and the z-transformation of scores within grade levels) did not allow the assessment of the developmental trends of motor competence and executive function. For the interpretation of the results, it should also be noted that computerized cognitive testing was performed in a group setting. While the surrounding noise was reduced and participants were seated with about 1 m distance between each other, it remains unclear to which extent distractions induced by the group setting influenced individual performance. Moreover, we performed path-analyses predicting executive function from motor competence due to the evidence that exercise with increased coordinative demands, which usually targets the promotion of motor competences, benefits abilities that are classified in this cognitive domain (Ludyga et al., 2020). However, a reverse direction of effects is currently discussed under the concept of automaticity (McClelland & Cameron, 2019). This concept argues that executive function is required to learn and master novel complex motor tasks, but that these demands decrease with a refinement of motor competences that promotes automaticity. Thus, our findings cannot explain the major direction of the association between motor competence and executive function and whether this direction differs across developmental periods. This also applies to sex differences, given that our study was not powered to compare the association of both constructs between boys and girls within each grade level. In the pooled analysis, an indication for sex differences was provided by boys compared to girls showing a statistically significant association between motor competences and working memory updating. However, this difference bears a risk for misinterpretation as the strengths of the associations did not differ between sexes for any executive function component.

5. Conclusion

In children, higher motor competences are generally associated with better executive function. However, for its subcomponents, there is a non-linear trend across grade levels. Motor competences have a predictive value for working memory and task-switching mainly in early

school years, with almost no time point showing a similar association for both components of executive function. In contrast, the relation between motor competence and inhibitory control reaches a low-to-moderate magnitude and appears to be temporally stable across all grades. These trends provide indications that interventions targeting executive function via the promotion of motor competences will yield more general or specific effects depending on the children's age.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sebastian Ludyga: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Christian Herrmann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2025.102895>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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